

Automatic assessment of free body diagrams using STACK

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Abstract: Free body diagrams are an important tool for solving mechanical problems involving force and moment balance. A STACK and JSXGraph based concept for interactive input and automatic evaluation of such diagrams is demonstrated. As a by-product, a generic JSXGraph block with an embedded object library for images of mechanical systems has been created. The library creates a high level layer of abstraction between the question author and the JSXGraph back-end. It reduces the authoring effort and facilitates overall consistency of the produced learning material.

Keywords: STACK; JSXGraph; free body diagram; assessment of graphical input

1 Introduction

The courses of engineering mechanics at THB make heavy use of weekly homework assignments with instant feedback based on Moodle tests. Since 2019, STACK³ questions [Sa13] increasingly replace the less powerful question types, mainly because of the better handling of multipart questions, algebraic input and flexible feedback options.

In engineering education, a key skill to develop is using graphs and sketches for model development and communication. For example, free body diagrams (FBD, details in the following section) are an essential step in deriving mathematical models for mechanical systems.

The sketching skills of the students being as heterogeneous as the hand-calc skills, a need for asynchronous individual training with instant feedback is obvious.

Without the ability to accept and evaluate graphical input, asynchronous training of such skills is limited to multiple choice questions, where the appropriate graphical representation for a given situation has to be selected. In the context of engineering mechanics, the lack of feedback on modelling steps like sketching FBDs has been criticised in the past [KBV19].

Fortunately, STACK comes with a built-in integration of JSXGraph⁴ based interactive widgets. The documentation covers the procedure how to build questions with interactive

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modification of existing objects in the widget. This approach has been widely used in the ITEMS⁵ project.

Another, less structured JSXGraph-based approach was shown in [MM19] for sketching function graphs. The students can move around control points, which leave a trace. This tries to mimic pen and pencil and is evaluated by computing of metrics for the proximity between the input and the reference solution. In order to avoid issues of object recognition, this approach isn't used here. Yet it would be an option if aspects of manual drawing precision were in the scope of assessment.

The present paper demonstrates that it is possible to enable interactive input and automatic assessment of FBDs for randomized questions within the framework of STACK.

2 Problem description

Problems in Engineering Mechanics usually consist of a system with given supports and external loads. Based on this, internal loads for later evaluation of structural integrity (does it break?) or stiffness (acceptable deflection?) have to be determined.

The forces acting at the supports (reactions) aren't usually known in advance. They rather emerge from the supports constraining the displacement of the system in a particular way. These reactions are to be determined using equilibrium conditions, the static version of Newton's second law.

An essential step in the solution process is to identify which particular reactions might emerge from the given supports. The result of this step is represented by the so called free body diagram. For unidirectional supports (e. g. at point *B* in figure 1), the direction of the reaction is known in advance, for general supports, both direction and magnitude are unknown and usually the reaction is represented by two unknown cartesian components (point *A* in figure 1).

It is important to note that there are no strict rules for naming and orientation of the components, as long as the vectors go through the point of application and the symbols are unique. This means that you can't directly compare equilibrium conditions (equations) entered by the student with a pre-defined teacher's answer. Instead you have to separately evaluate the correctness of the FBD and the consistency of the equations with that FBD.

Without an interface for entering and evaluating FBDs you are forced to either specify – instead of asking for – the FBD in the problem description (as in figure 1) or you can't provide feedback on the resulting equations and components of the reactions. You are then limited to FBD-independent final results, just like the magnitude.

⁵ itemspro.eu

Another aspect reflected in the FBD is the replacement of distributed loads by their resultants with correct magnitude, direction and location.

Fig. 1: Given system (left) and free body diagram (right). The distributed load has been replaced by its resultant.

3 Concept

The concept outlined here has been presented initially in October 2020 [Kr20].

In order to create a free body diagram based on a system sketch with parts, supports and loads, the following actions need to be performed:

- Remove the supports and eventually distributed loads from the sketch.
- Replace the removed objects by appropriate forces and moments (reactions and resultants). Quantities of unknown direction are represented by Cartesian components. Each force is characterized by location (point or line of action), direction and orientation (unit vector) and variable name or expression.

This means that individual elements need to be switchable between active and in-active state by the students. They must be able to add (and possibly delete) arrows, change their location and direction and to edit their label. Exact alignment is supported by grid snap or snap to objects. Therefore, in-active objects aren't really removed but rather greyed out.

The length of the arrows is insignificant, as these just represent unit vectors.

Internally, the entire sketch is represented by a Maxima list of lists. Each sub-list represents an object, see figure 2 or 4.

A generic JSXGraph block is placed in the question text. It contains a set of class definitions and functions for instantiation and modification, which are completely problem-independent. Thus, authoring questions with interactive input would not require touching any JavaScript code except from copy-pasting the generic block.

Fig. 2: Representation of objects by Maxima lists. The red dots are interactive control points

4 Demonstration

To demonstrate the feasibility of the approach in the context of STACK and JSXGraph, an interactive quiz was designed, where the user can create force and moment arrows, position them on the canvas and annotate them with names or expressions.

When the user presses "Check", the resultant of all forces in x - and y -direction and the resultant moment about a given point are displayed as nicely formatted symbolic expressions. This confirms that the user-selected names and unit vectors are available for later processing in the feedback variables (see figure 3).

The standard concept for communication between the CAS kernel (Maxima) and the JSXGraph widget uses JSON objects in a hidden text input field. However, due to security reasons, STACK doesn't evaluate Maxima code from text input fields. Therefore, an additional hidden input field of type algebraic is used to convey to Maxima the names and expressions supplied by the user.

A typical STACK question with interactive sketching of an FBD would consist of the following parts:

1. Question text with interactive JSXGraph widget, showing the original system (as in figure 1, left). The student has to de-activate the supports and distributed loads and add appropriately named forces and/or moments (as in figure 1, right).
2. Algebraic input of the equilibrium conditions.
3. Algebraic input of the support reactions (solution).

The students can solve the task with specific feedback after each step, where the correct solution for steps 2 and 3 depends on the choices made by the student in step 1. The feedback shown in figure 3 is exactly what would be teacher's answer for step 2 and thus demonstrates the feasibility of conveying the required data from the widget to the STACK response tree.

Tidy STACK question tool | Question

$$\Sigma F_x = -\frac{F_8}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{2 F_7}{\sqrt{5}} + A_x$$

$$\Sigma F_y = -3 a q_0 - g m + \frac{F_8}{\sqrt{2}} + \frac{F_7}{\sqrt{5}} - F + A_y$$

$$\Sigma M_0 = 9.9 a^2 q_0 + a g m + \frac{3 F_8 a}{\sqrt{2}} - \frac{F_7 a}{\sqrt{5}} - 2 F a - 3 A_y a - M_3 + M_0$$

JSXGraph v0.99.7 Copyright (C) see <http://jsxgraph.org>

- o + - ↓ ↑ →

Check

Fig. 3: STACK question, containing a widget with interactively generated forces and moments. The components of the resultant force and the resultant moment are displayed as algebraic expressions in the specific feedback.

5 Implementation and usage

As an intermediate step towards a mature implementation of the concept, a JSXGraph block with an embedded object library (working title "MecLib") has been designed. It is work in progress and has been published on Github⁶.

In order to define a sketch, the author of a STACK question has to specify a Maxima list of object descriptors in the question variables. As these descriptors are lists of string and numeric values, they are straightforward to randomize.

The approach has been applied to more than 80 questions in a course of engineering mechanics. Static images of various origin (handwriting, books, drawing programs) were replaced by dynamic randomized images of consistent appearance. As a bonus, the editable source of the images is embedded in the question variables section.

With the current set of objects, approximately 80% of the images can be replaced. The remainder are special cases, e. g. 3D images, not covered by the 2D object library or systems with complex geometric shapes.

No JSXGraph knowledge is required to apply the library. Just a generic JSXGraph block has to be copied to the question text section. It turns out that creating and debugging randomized images costs approximately 20% of the total time spent for authoring a question.

A cheat sheet and a selection of generated images are shown in fig. 4.

6 Further steps

In the near future, MecLib is applied to other courses of engineering mechanics like strength of materials and dynamics.

Currently, the generic JSXGraph block contains more than 700 lines of code for more than 20 objects. It is manually copy-pasted into the question by the author. In terms of portability and independence, this approach is safe. Yet the concept could benefit from a reference mechanism which could dynamically add blocks of external material to the question text and to the question variables sections. The source of such material might be a Moodle course file, an online resource or user-contributed content from the official STACK distribution.

Usage of a static JSXGraph block currently limits the concept to only a single widget in a given question. Sometimes additional widgets in the specific feedback of the response tree or in the general feedback would be required.

Moving on towards the initial idea of automatic assessment of FBDs requires activation/-deactivation methods for the objects as well as control objects of the editor user interface. The aim is to not bother the user with JSXGraph details even for the FBD editor.

⁶ <https://github.com/mkraska/meclib>

Fig. 4: MecLib cheat sheet along with a selection of sample images.

Significant effort will be required to streamline the evaluation of the user input. The identification of a set of useful generic helper functions is still ahead.

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